

CH30220/CH40220: Chemistry Thermodynamics in Context

Coursework: Scientific Commentary

Candidate Number: 23510

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YOUR Scientific COMMENTARY starts here:

Solvation, not conformational restriction, drives enthalpy-entropy compensation in molecular binding

- Drug design strategies should explicitly model binding-site water
- Further research should be conducted to clarify the relative roles of solvation and conformational restriction in enthalpy-entropy compensation

Context

Designing effective drugs requires understanding how strongly a molecule binds to its target. This strength is described by the Gibbs free energy of binding, a value that becomes more negative when a drug is more tightly bound.

Gibbs free energy has two components: enthalpy and entropy. Enthalpy describes how strong the interactions are when a drug binds to its target. Stronger bonds make enthalpy more favourable and help the drug “stick”. Entropy describes how much freedom the system has, so when binding restricts the movement of the drug, target protein, or surrounding environment, entropy becomes less favourable and works against this binding.

Due to these competing forces, changing a drug’s structure often alters enthalpy and entropy without changing the overall binding strength. This is known as enthalpy-entropy compensation (EEC) and is a major barrier in drug design. Traditionally, EEC was attributed to the drug or protein becoming more rigid upon binding, known as conformational restriction. However, Dragan et al. argue that water solvation plays a major role, as releasing or trapping tightly bound water molecules produces large enthalpy and entropy changes.

Methods

Dragan et al. use a narrative review methodology, summarising thermodynamic data from a wide range of published macromolecular binding studies to investigate the origins of EEC.

This analysis primarily uses thermodynamic data obtained from isothermal titration calorimetry studies which it integrates with structural information from crystallography and NMR. They examine various systems, including ligand–protein systems, protein–DNA interactions, and a protein–protein complex, to identify patterns in EEC and evaluate whether the observed entropy changes can be explained by conformational restriction alone.

Findings

The authors identify a consistent pattern of EEC across each interaction. In each system, the Gibbs free energy of binding remains relatively constant despite large changes in enthalpy and entropy. These compensatory shifts often exceed 50–100 kJ mol⁻¹, far greater than would be expected from conformational restriction alone.

As the degree of entropy change far exceeds the theoretical estimates of conformational entropy change in each system, they argue these large shifts are most likely due to the release or restriction of tightly bound water molecules at the protein binding site. In several examples, the number of water molecules released or trapped during binding matched the size and direction of the enthalpy and entropy changes.

This mechanism is intuitive: when ordered water molecules are released, the system gains freedom (higher entropy) but loses favourable interactions (enthalpy becomes less favourable), and trapping water does the opposite. These opposing effects cancel each

other out, suggesting that water reorganisation, rather than conformational restriction, is driving EEC.

They also propose a link between protein flexibility and bound water, suggesting that flexible proteins tend to hold on to fewer tightly bound water molecules whereas rigid proteins hold more.

This has important ramifications for drug design. Adding polar groups can disturb the water molecules around a binding site, causing this compensation effect. The authors propose that introducing ionic interactions to therapeutics could be a more reliable way to increase drug affinity.

Figure 1. (A) Unbound drug and protein, each solvated by water molecules. (B) Bound complex with water molecules trapped at the binding interface. When binding immobilises water in an ordered, ice-like arrangement, entropy decreases while favourable enthalpic interactions are gained. (C) Bound complex with water molecules released from the binding interface. When binding displaces ordered water into bulk solvent, entropy increases but favourable enthalpic interactions are lost.

Commentary

In this review, Dragan et al. reinterpret EEC, arguing that changes in water structure around a binding site, rather than conformational restriction, is the primary contributor to this effect. While solvation effects have long been recognised as important in drug-binding thermodynamics, the authors assign solvation effects as the dominant contributor to this phenomenon¹.

However, the strength of this argument is limited by the narrative nature of this review. As the authors focus exclusively on systems that strongly exhibit this compensation effect, instead of conducting a systematic analysis, their argument may suffer from selective bias. Additionally, many of its conclusions are based on inferences rather than direct measurements. For example, estimates of conformational entropy are approximate, and the proposed link between protein flexibility and bound water is speculative. Therefore, further experimental or computational studies explicitly designed to test these ideas would be needed to strengthen the argument.

Despite these limitations, this review aligns with the growing view that water plays an active role in determining how strongly molecules bind. This idea has increasingly been built into drug-design approaches, with many computational methods now explicitly modelling water molecules around protein binding sites^{2,3}. Recent studies suggest that ignoring these solvation effects has contributed to failures in structure-based drug discovery³.

Water-solvation effects undeniably play a role in EEC and should be considered in drug design, but whether they dominate to the extent suggested remains debated. Alternative

explanations, for example heat-capacity effects, statistical coupling and measurement artefacts, indicate that several factors may contribute to this compensation effect². Overall, the review highlights the importance of solvation in EEC, but its claim that this is the primary contributor across all systems is less convincing.

References

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3. Kaczor, A. A.; Zięba, A.; Matosiuk, D. The Application of WaterMap-Guided Structure-Based Virtual Screening in Novel Drug Discovery. *Expert Opinion on Drug Discovery* **2023**, 19 (1), 73–83. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17460441.2023.2267015>.

Original article

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